

Treatment of Carpet Effluents by Adsorption on Wollastonite

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Treatment of carpet effluents containing some chrome dyes, viz. omega chrome red ME (OCR), metomega chrome orange GL(MCO) and omega chrome fast blue B (OCB) by adsorption on wollastonite has been carried out. The maximum removal of dyes is noted at 10 mg dm⁻³ initial concentration, 30° temperature, pH 2.0 and 53 μm adsorbent particle size. The process of uptake follows first order rate expression and obeys Langmuir's model of adsorption. The coefficients of intraparticle diffusion and mass transfer are determined. The effect of temperature is found to be negative indicating exothermic nature of the process. Desorption study suggests the involvement of physicoadsorption.

The potential source of chrome dyes in natural water bodies includes waters from dyeing and washing processes of woollen carpets. The presence of these dyes in wastewater prevents reoxygenation by cutting of penetration of sunlight. This factor upsets the aquatic ecosystem¹. These waters have been found to be toxic and hazardous for plants and animals². Recently, it has been shown that higher concentrations of such dyes hamper soil fertility by suppressing the growth of nitrogen fixing cyanobacteria³. It is, therefore, essential to treat such effluents prior to being discharged. Because of limitations associated with chemical and biological methods employed for chrome dyes, the emphasis has been shifted to adsorption method⁴. The use of activated carbon is still popular but high cost restricts its use in developing countries like India.

The aim of the present study is to explore the feasibility of wollastonite in the treatment of carpet wastes rich in omega chrome red ME, metomega chrome orange GL and omega chrome fast blue B frequently used in carpet dyeing.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of wollastonite was found to be as follows : SiO₂, 48.52; CaO, 48.48; Fe₂O₃, 0.26; Al₂O₃, 0.24; mean particle diameter, 48.00 × 10⁻⁴ cm; surface area, 1.18 m²g⁻¹; density, 2.21 g cm⁻³; porosity, 0.23; pH_{ZPC}, 2.60. It is expected that adsorbate species

would be removed mainly by SiO₂ and Al₂O₃.

Effect of initial adsorbate concentration : Fig. 1 depicts that in all the cases the percentage removal of the dyes is maximum in low concentration range. This variation may be explained by the fact that 'parking space' for all the initial concentrations is constant while

Fig. 1. Effect of initial concentration on the removal of the dyes by wollastonite under optimum conditions.

the 'adsorbing species' are decreased in case of low initial concentration and vis-a-vis in higher concentration ranges. However, percentage adsorption varies almost linearly with respect to initial concentration. The following models have been developed to predict the percentage removal of various pollutants at any initial concentration :

For OCR, percentage removal = $144.54 C_0^{-0.28}$ (1)

For MCO, percentage removal = $118.08 C_0^{-0.24}$ (2)

For OCB, percentage removal = $137.56 C_0^{-0.40}$ (3)

Effect of adsorbent particle size : The percentage removal of OCR, MCO and OCB decreases respectively from 80.45 to 53.38, 73.04 to 64.26 and 58.37 to 38.80, with the increase in wollastonite particle size from 53 to 125 μm at 10 mg dm^{-3} initial concentration at 30° . This is because of greater surface area available using smaller adsorbent particle when the total mass of the adsorbent is constant⁵.

Fig. 2. Intraparticle diffusion plot for the adsorption of the dyes on wollastonite under optimum conditions.

Adsorption dynamics : The adsorption dynamics was studied considering the following steps.

Rate constant study : The Lagergren's rate equation as quoted by Trivedi *et al.*⁶ was used for the rate constant study of the systems,

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{k_{ad}}{2.303} t \quad (4)$$

The linear plots of $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t show the validity of equation (4) in the present cases, consequently first order nature of the process is involved herein. The values of adsorption rate constant (k_{ad}) for different systems were determined from the respective plots and noted in Table 1.

Intraparticle diffusion study : As the experiments were carried out in a rapidly stirred batch reactor, the

possibility of intraparticle diffusion could not be overlooked. This possibility was tested from the plots of amount adsorbed vs square root of time. It is clear from Fig. 2 that the plots are having dual character in each system. The initial curved portions are attributed to the boundary layer diffusion⁷ and the latter linear portions to the intraparticle diffusion⁸. The values of intraparticle rate parameter (k_p) were determined from the slopes of linear portions of respective plots and are recorded in Table 1.

Mass transfer study : The mass transfer study for adsorption of the dyes onto wollastonite was carried out using Furusawa and Smith⁹ model,

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_1}{C_0} - \frac{\beta_1}{1+mk} \right) = \ln \frac{mk}{1+mk} - \frac{1+mk}{mk} \beta_1 S_s t \quad (5)$$

A linear graphical relation between $\ln(C_1/C_0 - 1/1+mk)$ vs t was obtained, suggesting the validity of above model for the present study. The values of β_1 were calculated from the above plots (Table 1). The values of β_1 reveal that the velocity of the adsorbates transported from the liquid phase to solid phase is rapid enough to use the wollastonite for the treatment of wastewaters rich in the above dyes.

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR REMOVAL OF VARIOUS DYES BY ADSORPTION ON WOLLASTONITE UNDER OPTIMUM CONDITIONS

Dye	$10^{-2} k_{ad}$ min ⁻¹	$10^{-2} K_p$ mg g ⁻¹ min ^{1/2}	$10^{-6} \beta_1$ cm s ⁻¹
OCR	2.16	1.99	7.22
MCO	2.39	1.54	8.45
OCB	2.93	1.29	7.17

Adsorption isotherm : The adsorption data fits well in the rearranged form of the Langmuir adsorption model,

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{Q^o b} + \frac{C_e}{Q^o} \quad (6)$$

The linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e at 30° show the applicability of the above model in the present system indicating the formation of monolayer coverage of adsorbate on the surface of adsorbent.

Effect of temperature : In all the systems, temperature has a negative effect, consequently exothermic nature of the process. It has been observed that the percentage removal of OCR, MCO and OCB decreased from 80.45 to 59.40, 73.04 to 60.19 and 58.37 to 40.47 respectively, at 10 mg dm⁻³ concentration by increasing the temperature from 30 to 50°. This variation is due to increase in escaping tendency of the adsorbate species from the surface of the adsorbent. The percentage removal is correlated with the temperature and the following relations are obtained :

$$\text{For OCR, percentage removal} = 198.87 T^{-0.29} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{For MCO, percentage removal} = 315.88 T^{-0.43} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{For OCB, percentage removal} = 454.17 T^{-0.60} \quad (9)$$

The temperature effect can also be explained from the thermodynamic study. The standard free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) changes were calculated at different temperatures using the equations,

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta H^\circ = R \left(\frac{T_2 T_1}{T_2 - T_1} \right) \ln \frac{K_2}{K_1} \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T} \quad (12)$$

The negative values of ΔG° (-1.200, -0.858 and -1.085 kcal mol⁻¹ at 30° for OCR, MCO and OCB respectively) indicate that the process involved is spontaneous in nature. The values of ΔH° (-10.79, -4.62 and -11.90 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively, for OCR, MCO and OCB) show the exothermic nature of the process. Also, the negative values of ΔS° (-31.91, -12.37 and -35.92 cal mol⁻¹ for OCR, MCO and OCB, respectively) suggest the possibility of favourable adsorption¹⁰.

Effect of pH : The extent of removal of OCR, MCO and OCB by wollastonite decreases from 92.37 to 15.06, 78.08 to 12.13 and 65.07 to 12.32% respectively, at 10 mg dm⁻³ concentration and 30° with the increase in pH from 2.0 to 12.0. The following correlations between percentage removal and pH were obtained,

$$\text{For OCR, percentage removal} = 256.37 \text{ pH}^{-1.03} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{For MCO, percentage removal} = 549.54 \text{ pH}^{-1.44} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{For OCB, percentage removal} = 140.04 \text{ pH}^{-0.81} \quad (15)$$

Moreover, the variation in adsorption of the above species with pH may be explained on the basis of following approaches.

Aqua-complex formation approach : Since the wollastonite is rich in a number of metallic oxides, it forms the aqua-complexes coming in contact with water. Subsequently, a positive or negative charge is developed at the surface of wollastonite on acid-base interaction as :

(Acidic interaction)

(Basic interaction)

where M stands for Al, Ca Si, etc. It is obvious from the above equilibria that with decrease in pH of the solution the positive charge density on the surface increases and hence the enhancement of the adsorption of the dyes which is anionic in nature.

Surface complexation approach : At solid-solution interface surface complex is formed due to interaction of hydroxylated surface (SOH), protons and dye anions as per the mechanism,

Thus, it is obvious that for a maximum removal of the dyes, the presence of protons on the surface of the adsorbents is essential which is possible only in the acidic range. That is why acidic range is favourable for a high removal of the dyes.

Desorption study :

The extent of desorption of OCR, MCO and OCB from the surface of wollastonite laden with 0.60, 0.56 and 0.41 mg g⁻¹ of the respective dye, increases from

12.70 to 100, 16.15 to 88.26 and 28.77 to 94.60% respectively, with the increase in pH from 5.0 to 12.0 at 30°. At neutral pH, the percentage desorption of OCR, MCO and OCB is 37.58, 38.70 and 45.80 respectively, under similar conditions. Thus, a significant desorption of OCB at neutral pH is indicative of weak bonding with the active centres of the adsorbent.

Conclusion: The optimum conditions for the dyes are as follows: initial concentration is 10 mg dm⁻³ and temperature is 30° for all the dyes, and pH is 4.2 for OCR, 4.5 for MCO and 3.5 for OCB.

Wollastonite can be effectively used for the treatment of carpet effluents rich in OCR, MCO and OCB, particularly at low range of concentration, temperature and pH. Similarly, the quality of the secondary effluent from the carpet units can be markedly improved by the use of wollastonite as an adsorbent.

Experimental

The dyes OCR, MCO and OCB were donated by M/s. Sandoz India Ltd. All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent (B.D.H.) grade. The wollastonite was supplied by M/s. Wolkem Pvt. Ltd., Udaipur (Rajasthan). It was passed through 53, 75 and 125 μm sieves and used as such. The average particle size was measured by a HIAC-320 (Royco Instruments, U.S.A.) analyser, and the surface charge by Lazer Zee Meter 500 (Penkem, U.S.A.). The surface area was determined by a 'three point' N₂ gas adsorption method using a Quantasorb QS17 (Quantachrome, U.S.A.) analyser and the porosity by a mercury porosimeter. Standard methods¹¹ were employed to analyse the adsorbent.

Treatment experiments were carried out by shaking the sample (1.0 g) of wollastonite with aqueous solution (50 ml) of various pollutant species of desired concentration, temperature and pH in different glass bottles in a shaking thermostat with a constant speed of 125 rpm. At the end of pre-selected intervals of time, the adsorbent was removed by centrifugation and the progress of reaction was assessed spectrophotometrically (Spectronic-20, Bausch and Lomb) at respective λ_{max}. Desorption studies were made by agi-

tating the adsorbent (1.0 g) laden with a definite amount of adsorbent with distilled water (50 ml) in the pH range 5.0–12.0.

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Nomenclature

C_0	Initial concentration of pollutant species, mg dm ⁻³
q_e	Amount of the dyes adsorbed at equilibrium mg g ⁻¹
q	Amount of the dyes adsorbed at time t , mg g ⁻¹
k_{ad}	Rate constant for adsorption, min ⁻¹
t	Contact time, min
C_t	Concentration of pollutant species at time t , mg dm ⁻³
m	Mass of wollastonite particle per unit volume of particle free slurry, g dm ⁻³
k	Langmuir constant (Q^0b), dm ³ g ⁻¹
β_1	Mass transfer coefficient, cm s ⁻¹
S_s	Outer surface of wollastonite particle per unit volume of particle free slurry, cm ⁻¹
T	Temperature, °C
SOH	Hydrated surface of wollastonite

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